

The Wonder of the Kakatiya art- Ramappa temple

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ABSTRACT

India is a treasure house of numerous heritage monuments. The ruins at Hampi stand in testimony of the distinguished ancient times; the iconic Taj Mahal is the evidence of the glorious medieval Indian History. The Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj Terminus signifies the contributions of British during the modern era. All of these are “World Heritage Sites” – a status inscribed by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). India continues to assert the claim for “World Heritage Site” to many such architectural masterpieces and heritage monuments. This paper tries to analyze the process of getting inscribed as a World Heritage Site and the benefits of the inscription. The paper is focused on the first World Heritage Site of the state of Telangana- The Ramappa temple, its peculiar features and its journey of claiming the most acclaimed tag conferred by UNESCO.

Key words: UNESCO, World Heritage Site, Ramappa Temple.

Introduction

India has countless monuments, structures which tell us the tales of the glorious past. These skilfully carved structures provide with valuable insights into contemporary socio-cultural lives of the people. The skills of artisans also depict meaningful discourses from the mythologies and the epics of India. This combination of architectural mastery together with meaningful narratives has always been one of the attractions for the people from worldwide.

The world and international organizations such as the UNESCO are conscious about the unique heritage India holds custody of and thus, recognizes it through UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization). In 2021, two such sites, Dholavira – a Harappan city and (Rudreshwara) Ramappa Temple from Telangana became the “World Heritage sites” recognized by the UNESCO.

Objectives- 1. To illustrate unique features of the Ramappa Temple.

2. To restate technological expertise used in the construction of the Ramappa temple.

3. To attempt drawing inferences from the sculptures, stories engraved on the pillars of the temple.

4. To briefly discuss the process of getting inscribed as World Heritage Site by the UNESCO with special reference to the Ramappa Temple.

Methodology- The research is carried out based on qualitative research methodology. There is abundant literature available in the open domain regarding the temple, architectural features and its journey towards getting the UNESCO World Heritage Site tag. Both, primary and secondary sources have been referred to carry out research regarding the Ramappa Temple. To name a few, the nomination Dossier of the Ramappa temple, Annual Report of the year 2019-2020 prepared by Council on Monuments and Sites in India (COMOS) and (Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention, 2019) were referred to study about the temple in detail. Additionally, articles from the leading newspapers like Indian Express, Hindustan Times have given great inputs towards understanding significance of the architectural marvel. Observations noted by eminent scholars like G.S.V. Suryanarayan Murty, P V Narsimha Rao further illustrate the wonder of the kakatiyan times.

The UNESCO and “World Heritage site” tag

UNESCO inscribes “World Heritage Site” status to the monuments based on ten criteria, out of which at least one criteria needs to be satisfied for getting in the recognition. These ten criteria are precisely mentioned in the “Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention”. This document is regularly revised by the “World Heritage Committee” which is in charge of the implementation of the convention. Efforts are made to include new concepts, knowledge and experiences upon each revision of the document. Some of the criteria for the tag of “World Heritage Site” are as follows-

1. A location with an “Outstanding Universal Value”.
2. A location having cultural and/or natural significance which is so exceptional as to transcend national boundaries and to be of common importance for present and future generations of all humanity.
3. A location representing a masterpiece of human creative genius.
4. A location exhibiting an important interchange of human values over a span of time or within a cultural area of the world.

(Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention, 2019)

The World Heritage Site upon receiving the tag is entitled to get assistance under the “World Heritage Fund”. (Gill & A, 2021)

Ramappa temple becoming “World Heritage Site”

Ramappa temple in spite of being an architectural marvel was not getting its due recognition. The Efforts towards appreciation of the masterpiece started long back in 2009 after BV Papa Rao, former IAS officer established the “Kakatiya Heritage Trust”. Efforts were also made towards spreading awareness regarding the need to conserve the temple. Ramappa temple was in the tentative list of UNESCO world Heritage Sites since 2014. After the formation of the independent state of Telangana, a proposal was prepared with the help of historians for the recognition of Ramappa temple as a UNESCO “World Heritage Site” by Papa Rao, who had become an advisor for Chief Minister K Chandrashekar Rao by then. Ramappa temple was the only nomination from India for the tag of “World Heritage Site” in 2019. After getting through the tentative list, Ramappa temple’s heritage status was evaluated by the International Council of Historic Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS). In November 2019, Mr Papa Rao and his delegation went to Paris for explaining about the outstanding universal value of the temple site. Finally, in the 44th session of World Heritage Committee of UNESCO held in Fuzhou (China) where 17 out of 21 member states supported the nomination of Ramappa Temple as “World Heritage Site” on July 25, 2021. (telanganas-ramappa-temple-a-kakatiya-era-marvel-named-after-sculptor, 2021)

The temple is having the nomination under Criterion I (Masterpiece of human creative genius) and Criterion III (bearing a unique or at least an exceptional testimony to a cultural tradition, which is living or which has disappeared). This is a significant achievement as the temple, from now on, is entitled to get financial assistance for protection of its cultural and natural heritage, international assistance that can support projects related to emergency, conservation and

management, and for preparatory assistance under the national tentative list. The site will also have access to global project management resources if a repair is needed. The site, by default, will also receive protection under the Geneva Convention, in events of war. India will also receive expert advice from the World Heritage Committee to support activities for the preservation of the site. (Murthy G. S., 2017)

Ramappa temple

➤ *Introduction* –The Ramappa temple is situated in a small village Palampet of Venkatpur Mandal, located in Mulug district, approximately 66 Kilometres away from Warangal. A 201 line Telugu inscription in the temple premises mentions, the temple is built by Racherla Rudra Reddy –a minister/commander in the court of Kakatiya King Ganapati Deva. The temple dates back to 1213 CE. It is believed that, it took 40 years for the completion of the construction of the temple. Shiva- the main deity in the temple is being worshipped by the name of Ramlingeswara, thus the temple being called as Ramlingeswara temple as well. Ramappa was the chief sculptor of the temple, thus the temple is also known by his name. This might be the only instance of a structure being known by the name of its chief sculptor.(Bhalerao, 2021)

➤ *Structure*-Ramappa temple, presents a classical style of structures. It chiefly depends on its spatial organization, constructed intricately in a design of a star. The temple faces East- towards the rising sun, according to the principles of ‘Vastu Shastra’. The temple complex houses Kateshwara temple dedicated to Lord Kateswara and Kameshwar Temple, now known as ‘Kalyan Mandapa’. Pakashala, in the complex was used for preparing the food which was served to the devotees.

At the entrance of the temple is Nandi Mandapam with Nandi –facing the Lord Shiva shrine. The structure is famous for the skilfully carved ornamentation of Nandi, panels of Vedi Bandh with floral designs, designs showing elephants, musicians etc. Nandi in the temple is shown in an attentive posture, as if ready to take and execute the command of the Lord. From every angle, Nandi appears to look at the on-lookers. (Gill & A, ramappa-13th-century-telangana-temple-unesco-tag-, 2021)

The temple is placed on a star shaped Upapitha, built on a raised platform (6 feet high). This is a symbolic division. The temple is represented as a connecting link between heaven and earth, by being in the middle of the both.

It consists of a Garbhagriha where the shivalingam is placed at a height of approximately 9 feet. At the entrance of Garbhagriha, the walls are decorated with representations depicting various dance forms, different musical instruments. Its ceiling consists of carvings, depicting scenes from Hindu epics Ramayana, Shiva Purana, "Samudramanthan", "Daksha Yadnya", "Daksha Sanhar" "Tripursurwadh", "Gajasurwadh" and various other ancient texts. The temple also has an antarala, and maha mandapam. The sanctum is surrounded by pradakshina path. The Vimana of the temple shrine is made up of bricks reducing the overall weight of the temple. The scientific studies show the bricks used for the constructing the Vimana of the temple were made with wood powder thus on burning them they became lightweight so much so, that the bricks can float on water too. (Team of GSV Suryanarayana Murthy, 2017)

Ramappa temple is constructed with locally available materials such as; Sandstone, Granite and Dolerite etc. The establishment of the temple is according to the "Sand box" technology. While filling the creator created for the construction of temple, sand-lime-jaggery was used. This mixture acts as barrier in case of earthquakes. During the earthquakes, the waves causing the earthquake get assimilated into sand filling, causing no damage to the structure. Thus, in spite of the incidences of earthquakes in the 17th century, there has been no damage to the temple. (Bhalerao, 2021)

The genius of the architect is seen in the idea of using modular chiselled blocks of sculptures that could be assembled on the site in a particular order without using any mortar. A verse inscribed outside the temple says, "In this exceedingly brilliant city, Rudra, who was a terror to rival warriors, performed the consecration of Rudreshwara. On top of the temple, shines distinctly a golden cupola, like the bright sun on the lofty peak of the eastern mountains, illuminating the space of the sky."

The sculptures converse their history – for instance, there is a breathtaking representation of a dance form, Perini Siva Tandavam, developed by JayapaSenani, a commander and relative of celebrated Kakatiya Ruler, Ganapathi Deva, on the temple walls and on the panels on ceilings.

There is a hall in front of the sanctum sanctorum with four pillars. These pillars were skilfully placed with mathematical perfection.

- *Sculptures at Ramappa temple*- The temple is famous for the brilliantly carved out sculptures. They too are sculpted according to the guidelines mentioned in 'shilpa sastra'. The highlights of the temple are the bracket figures of two types- madanikas of Palampet and Vyalas.

Madanikas are the beautiful maidens in the roles of Nagini, Manini, Rati, Mardala, Dalamalika, Huntress and Dancer. Dalamalika is a woman, standing in a dancing posture garlanding her own self. She is shown wearing high heels.

The figure of Nagini standing on coiled serpent, holding other ones around the shoulders and in the lifted hands portrays beauty of womanhood. It displays attainment of Siddhi beyond the consciousness of physical bodies. Rati is shown holding the sugarcane symbolizing love. Gayani is a singer standing in tribhanga position; she has two drummers on her both sides. Mardala is shown holding mridanga, she is standing in dwibhanga position surrounded by musicians. Abhinaya nartaki and nartaki are shown with dancing positions with drummers along side. As mentioned earlier too, another remarkable sculpture is of Jayassinartaki standing in dancing position as described by Jaya Senapati in book Nritta Ratnavali. She is shown wearing circular earrings. There are small figurines finely carved out around the main sculpture. Huntress Madanika is shown holding bow and arrow. She is wearing costume adorned with rows of flowers. Gayani Nartaki is singing while giving her dance performance. (Team of GSV Suryanarayana Murthy, 2017)

Another remarkable feature of the temple is Gaja-Vyala brackets. It is a mythical monster shown standing firmly on the head and raised trunk of an elephant. Their protruding tongue and tusks, reptile like dexterity, short but cunning ears, and bulging bellicose eyes and above all the fierce, aggressive and terrifying expression on their faces are splendidly set out by the master craftsmen of the period. They are placed at the eaves of sabhamandapa. They appear to be the protectors of the temple, discharging their duty religiously. (Team of GSV Suryanarayana Murthy, 2017)

The pillars of the temple are decorated with the intricate carvings too. The sculptures on the pillars are carved in a three dimensional form with so much precision that a needle can be passed through these minute details of the sculptures. It was appreciated by PV Narasimha Rao, the then Prime Minister of India in following words- "The ornamentation of the pillars of the Mandapa, architrave of the antharala and the ceiling of the Ranga Mandapa are rich, subtle and fine like exquisite filigree work on gold or silver indeed." (Narsimharao, 1966)

- *Ramappa temple and Vandalism*-It can be rightly said, that the heritage in India is ill-fated considering the incidences of vandalism inflicted upon it. Ramappa temple was no exception to it. On December 13, 1916, Ghulam Yazdani of the Nizam's Archaeology Department found two sculptures of the temple below the platform. Reportedly, they were removed by one of the district officers in order to use them to decorate his house. This attempt of vandalism was curbed with the efforts of Ghulam Yazdani. However, it highlights the apathy Indians have towards the rich heritage acquired from the ancestors. (Nanisetti, 2021)

- *Ramappa temple in popular culture*-Ramappa temple has been an attraction right from the earlier times till very recently. Eminent personalities have mentioned Ramappa temple in their memoirs and travelogues.

The famous Italian merchant and explorer Marco Polo has stated the temple to be the “brightest star in the galaxy of medieval temples of the Deccan.” Former Prime Minister of India PV Narasimha Rao penned down “Symphony in Stone” promoting the beauty of Ramappa temple in 1966. He wrote- “Indeed, in the hands of the sculptors, the hard black basalt virtually attained the softness of wax and the polish of a clean mirror.” He was amazed by the artistry so much that opined - “To describe the temple of Ramappa is to demonstrate the inadequacy of the written word”. (Narsimharao, 1966)

Kakatiya Heritage Trust also launched a book titled as “Ramappa Temple – Crest Jewel of Kakatiya Art and Architecture” written by Dr Choodamani Nandagopal marking the occasion of the visit of the UNESCO appointed ICOMOS Expert for evaluation of India's 2020 nomination as a World Heritage Site.(Service H. N., kakatiya-heritage-trust-launches-a-book-on-ramappa-temple, 2019)

While people from far away were appreciating the beauty of the temple, Mandala Malla Reddy, believed to be a descendant of Racherla Rudra also gathered a lot of data and compiled a book about Ramappa temple titled as “Ramappa Gudi”.

The temple has inspired the poets as well and Gnanpeeth awardee Dr C Narayana Reddy wrote a musical story titled ‘Ramappa,’ dedicated to Dr Puttaparthi Sreenivasacharyulu who spent his entire life on archaeological research, to Indian archaeologist Ghulam Yazdani, many people who did their bit in protecting the temple.

The contribution of Ramappa temple was not limited to stories and poems. The temple helped throw light on Perini Sivatanavam which was a Kakatiya-era warrior dance form performed by the men which was revived by dance guru Nataraja Ramakrishna. (Nanisetti, 2021)

- *Ramappa temple and tourist attraction*- One of the staff of the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI) has reported increase in the number of visitors to Palampet from about 500 to over 2,000 per day after the temple received World Heritage Site Tag. Locals who are dependent on the temple for their livelihood are very happy. There are some 40 petty businesses including eateries in the vicinity of the temple. A local businessman shared that a business of worth 50,000/- Rs is easily made with 500 tourists visiting the temple every day and now it can go on increasing with the new recognition. The higher inflow of tourists is already having an impact on the local economy. Locals are quoting higher prices for land in and around the village. Agricultural land was sold for some 15 lakh Rupees earlier which is now expected to be sold out at 25 lakh Rupees.(Sridhar, 2021)

- *Ramappa temple and local economy-* In Medieval Deccan history, large shrines were not just religious places. They were hubs of social, economic and cultural activity. With huge land grants made by rulers, temples also donned the role of landlord, employer and a power centre as a seat of village Panchayats. They also played a role in local agriculture with the attached tank providing irrigation to fields in the vicinity.

In the good old days, the Ramappa temple had a huge tank spread over 12 km, though now it has shrunk to about 3 km. But the dam and water channels originally built by the Kakatiyas are still intact and offering succour to surrounding fields even today. (Sridhar, 2021)

- *Ramappa temple and future-* The Telangana Government is drawing up plans to woo foreign and domestic tourists by offering a temple circuit and packaged tours. The ASI too has its own plans. It remains to be seen how far these initiatives will go in attracting more visitors in the days to come – especially with the pandemic still raging.

Discussion The Ramappa Temple - built using the locally available material like Granite, Sandstone, and Dolerite, with an indigenous technique to keep the temple earthquake resistant signifies the visionary thought process of the architect towards creating a fine piece of art. The sculptures carved out with extensive details from the diversified stories mentioned in the ancient texts, madanikas and mythical monster Gaja-Vyala emphasis on the role of this temple which goes beyond being just a religious place. Construction of the temple done with the help of basic tools like knife, chisel and hammer further highlights the expertise and skills of the artisans. All of these combined together justify the World Heritage Site status inscribed to the temple by the UNESCO.

Conclusion The Ramappa temple stands as a proof of the rich heritage our ancestors have left for us. The UNESCO has honoured the efforts and expertise of the architects for creating such a masterpiece. The heritage monuments like the Ramappa temple converse with the visitors, onlookers and do take us back to the times when it was constructed. Thus, preserving this treasure received almost free of cost is a responsibility to be shared by all.

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